

TENDENCY TO COSMOPOLITANISM IN MODERN MORAL EDUCATION

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ANNOTATION: This article highlights the characteristics of national moral education in the life of our society, the types of values, the role of values in human life.

Key words: value, society, people, morality, development, independence, human, thought.

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A person's moral life is closely related to his moral education. After all, moral education is one of the continuous processes that ensure the development of a person as a person. In it, the individual realizes moral values, stabilizes moral qualities in himself, learns to live on the basis of moral principles and norms. Moral education seeks answers to two important questions throughout the history of mankind: one of them is how to live, and the other is what to do. The process of searching for answers to these questions is a practical form of moral education. There is a saying that education begins in the mother's womb. Its original meaning is that, first of all, the parents themselves should have received moral education. After all, a bird does what it sees in its nest: the father and mother should set a high example of morality in the family. It should also be noted that the materialistic view that morality is created in a person only through moral education has been dominant for many years. True, the importance of moral education is extremely great. But morality is a divine gift given to man as the most important of his

human characteristics. We improve this spiritual blessing - the foundation with the help of moral education. Otherwise, we would be able to raise moral beings from monkeys and dogs. Thus, moral education is one of the ways to bring a human child to perfection. He has many tools. Some of them are traditional means of education, and another part are modern means. Usually, both types of tools are used. For example, in pre-school moral education, traditional education through fairy tales and narratives and modern education through toys and games are successfully used; in this, the child is encouraged not to be hot-tempered, arrogant, to be honest with the help of games.

Television, radio, puppet theater, cinema play a big role in children's moral education. In general, art is the most powerful tool of moral education. This tool covers all sections of the population, people of different ages. Especially, the fiction type of art is extensive. Works published in genres ranging from fairy tales to novels play a huge role in the moral formation of a person. Through them, the reader, as a student, has an artistic perception of what is good and evil; they are also important in choosing an ideal. In addition, there are collections of stories, narrations and advices directly intended for moral education in fiction, which, as we saw above, we call pandnoms: "Kalila and Dimna", "Nightmare", "Gulistan", "Zarbulmasal" Classical works have served as a means of traditional moral education for many centuries and generations, and will continue to do so. The way of moral education that is relevant for all times is the principle of exemplification. In the family, first of all, as mentioned above, parents should be a moral example for the child. It should not be overlooked that teachers are accepted by their students as a personal example, from the teaching methods to the "small" actions of teachers in schools and universities. Etiquette, honesty, truthfulness in teacher-disciple relationships are among the factors that ensure the formation of moral education of young people. Currently, television can be cited as the most powerful modern tool of moral education. It has the ability to screen and display works created in almost all types of art. In addition, regular programs dedicated to special moral education are also broadcasted there. Uzbek-language programs

such as "O'talar sozi - aql'n kozi", "Rivayat", "Aqshom Ertaklari" are examples of this. Therefore, television should never become an enterprise of songs that promote lightness, pornographic ads, and video films that harden the human heart. It is appropriate to add with. In this sense, it is noteworthy that people influence each other without giving advice or teaching manners. Moral maturity begins with mastery of manners. Etiquette is a characteristic expression of moral culture. Ethical culture requires only the same regulated behavior for a specific situation. The scope of ethical culture is so wide that it includes from ordinary human relations to internationally accepted rules of behavior. For example, the etiquette of a political figure, the ethical culture of hospitality, the etiquette of a host, etc. Along with modern forms of moral culture, there are also national-traditional forms, without which it is difficult to imagine the life of any nation.

For example, let's take greeting etiquette. According to the rules of moral culture, a person crossing the street should greet the people standing in front of the gate or in the street, in this posture, the right hand should be on the left chest, above the heart, and the head should be bowed slightly. In the culture of seeing, waving the hand indicates rudeness and disdain towards the person you are seeing. That is, through moral culture, the strict rules of etiquette are implemented through beautiful behavior. A need, a necessity for a good person, a healthy person suffers mentally without it, his mood drops. The second master expresses his attitude with a momentary glance. The first master with facial expression and handwriting - movement; From the point of view of the second master, if it means "Obbo Shouvoz - hey, you're in a hurry - yes, it's okay, there's no harm, that's fine." You can hear the words: "You've disgraced your work again - damn you, when will you become a man?!". Undoubtedly, if the first master observed manners in behavior, the second one shows his opposite - not his student's, but his own indecency. z - is noteworthy as a means of self-education. For this reason, forming the manners of behavior in our youth is one of the important tasks facing our society today. In this, the influence of parents and neighborhood is great. You need to be able to use it. Because the achievement of moral perfection begins with mastering the manners

of behavior. Ethical culture is one of the most visible forms of relationships, and this is etiquette. He mostly controls the external culture of a person, the fulfillment of the rules of self-behavior in mutual relations. Some of them are traditional means of education, and another part are modern means. Usually, both types of tools are used. For example, in pre-school moral education, traditional education through fairy tales and narratives and modern education through toys and games are successfully used; in this, the child is encouraged not to be hot-tempered, arrogant, to be honest with the help of games. Television, radio, puppet theater, cinema play a big role in children's moral education. In general, art is the most powerful tool of moral education. This tool covers all sections of the population, people of different ages. Especially, the fiction type of art is extensive. Works published in genres ranging from fairy tales to novels play a huge role in the moral formation of a person. Through them, the reader is very important as an educator. In addition, there are collections of stories, narrations and advices directly intended for moral education in fiction, which, as we saw above, we call pandnoms: "Kalila and Dimna", "Nightmare", "Gulistan", "Zarbulmasal". Classical works have served as a means of traditional moral education for many centuries and generations, and will continue to do so. The principle of exemplification is the way of moral education that is relevant for all times. In the culture of seeing, waving the hand indicates rudeness and disdain towards the person you are seeing. There is another aspect of moral culture: in it we can see the harmony of decency and beauty. The second master expresses his attitude with a momentary glance.

Summary:

In the family, first of all, as mentioned above, parents should be a moral example for the child. It should not be overlooked that teachers are accepted by their students as a personal example, from the teaching methods to the "small" actions of teachers in schools and universities. It is desirable to combine moral education with mental, spiritual and physical education. Then our society will become a fully

developed civil society. All legal and social conditions have been created for this in our country.

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